

Katarzyna Janic compiled the questionnaire. It is part of the Polonez Bis project ‘Towards grammatical iconicity of language: a crosslinguistic study of P demotion constructions’. The collected data will serve to design a semantic map that operates under iconicity assumption, i.e. crosslinguistically recurrent similarity in form reflects similarities in meaning.

Crosslinguistic studies show that many languages have several valency and voice alternation types that share two defining characteristics: (i) they syntactically demote the P¹ argument, (ii) but they do not affect the argument structure of the verb. Hence, the agent remains agent, and the patient remains patient. Consequently, the constructions resulting from such voice and valency alternations display a formal and semantic overlap. They may include but are not limited to antipassive, conative, noun incorporation, and indefinite P omission constructions. These are traditionally discussed as individual alternation types across languages.

For the purpose of our research, we gather the voice and valency alternations sharing the (i)-(ii) features under the umbrella term of P DEMOTION ALTERNATIONS. These consist of a transitive construction from which syntactically intransitive P DEMOTION CONSTRUCTIONS are derived. The P demotion alternations are triggered by the operation performed on the transitive verb that targets the P argument. As a result, the P argument is syntactically demoted (or ‘downgraded’), and as a result, it no longer functions as a core argument. This can be indicated by the loss of argument coding properties of P and/or P omission. We called such an operation P DEMOTION OPERATION. According to a different degree of syntactic demotion of the initial P, its referent can either be expressed as a peripheral oblique (or ‘adjunct’) argument or be completely unexpressed. The constructions with unexpressed P mean that they do not include an NP that would correspond to the initial P. Hence, they can be analyzed in terms of P incorporation, P suppression, or P omission. In the literature, such constructions are sometimes discussed under ‘complete demotion’ (Givón 2001: 172; Zúñiga & Kittilä 2019: 106). Given the above, we distinguish the following P demotion constructions:

1. P demotion construction with an oblique argument (§3)
2. P demotion construction with an incorporated P argument (§4)
3. P demotion construction with a suppressed P argument (§5)
4. P demotion construction with an omitted P argument (§6)

Generally, P demotion alternations encompass verb-coded valency (i.e. voice) and verb-uncoded valency alternations. For the purposes of our research, we lump them together, arguing that they form a family of constructions called the P DEMOTION DOMAIN. Our focus is on the morphosyntactic properties of P demotion constructions as well as the functional properties of the P argument, such as affectedness, referentiality, and animacy.

The questionnaire is organized as follows. First, it includes general questions about the language and the author (§1). Then, it addresses the morphosyntactic properties of a language (§2). Finally, §3-§6 ask about each P demotion construction individually. For the sake of clarity, some subsections start with a short explanation and illustrative example(s).

How to fill out the questionnaire:

- The questionnaire contains a) YES and b) NO answers. Please add **x** next to the correct answer. The c) answer is empty. It offers the possibility to add a comment when a YES or NO answer needs further explanation. If neither YES nor NO answer works for your language, please use c) for a clarification note.

¹A and P are generalized roles, they refer to the core arguments coded like agents and patients of core transitive verbs respectively, whilst S defines the core argument of intransitive constructions with coding properties corresponding to that of the unique argument of major monovalent verbal predicates (Creissels 2016: 28).

Polonez Bis questionnaire on the P demotion domain

- **Since the questionnaire is lengthy, the respondents are not obliged to complete all the questions. The questions in §1-§2 are obligatory. Then, a respondent is invited to select **at least one** P demotion alternation from §3, §4, §5, or §6 and provide the answers.**

1. Introduction

1.1. Please provide the name of your language and the language family.

The name of your language:

The name of your language family:

1.2. Please provide your email address.

E-mail address:

1.3. Please provide the date of sending the questionnaire.

Date:

2. Morphosyntax

2.1. Please provide a glossed basic construction with a prototypically transitive verb.

A verb is prototypically transitive if it codes an event, implying a maximum degree of semantic transitivity. It includes two nominal arguments representing a prototypical agent and a patient, where none shows evidence of syntactic demotion. As we are interested in encoding properties of verbal arguments, the nominals should be overtly expressed (at least in dependent-marking languages). If your language is head-marking, look into constructions with (1st/2nd person) pronominal A and P arguments, as 3rd person arguments are often not indexed on the verb.

2.2. Are A and P arguments of the verb flagged (by case or adposition)?

- a) yes.....
- b) no.....
- c)

2.3. Are A and P arguments indexed on the verb (by agreement/cross-referencing)?

- a) yes.....
- b) no.....
- c)

2.4. Is the system of grammatical relations in basic (affirmative/declarative) clauses organized according to a nominative/accusative, ergative/absolutive, tripartite, some other system?

- a) yes.....
- b) no.....
- c)

2.5. Is there some split in the marking of the A and P arguments?

- a) yes.....
- b) no.....
- c)

2.6. Can an anaphorically retrievable P be left unexpressed, or is it obligatorily expressed by an index or a pronoun?

- a) yes.....
- b) no.....
- c)

3. P oblique

The P demotion operation may syntactically downgrade the P argument from the core to the oblique, peripheral status in a clause. The loss of the core argument status, which can be triggered in some languages by a voice marker, entails a change in the P encoding properties (e.g. flagging and/or indexing). For instance, in (1b), the P argument *load* is no longer indexed on the verb, and it carries an oblique instrumental case. In (2b), the P argument is flagged by the oblique preposition *at*. While alternation (1) is known as antipassive, the one in (2) is discussed as conative alternation or an oblipatient alternation (Haspelmath 2022: 16).

1. Chukchi (Chukotko-Kamchatkan; Kozinsky et al. 1988: 652)

- a. $\text{?Aa}\check{\text{c}}\text{ek}=\text{a}$ $\text{kimit?}=\text{an}$ $\text{ne}=\text{nl?etet}=\text{an}$
 youth-ERG load=ABS 3PL=carry=3SG/AOR
 ‘(The) young men carried away the load.’
- b. $\text{?Aa}\check{\text{c}}\text{ek}=\text{at}$ $\text{ine}=\text{nl?etet}=\text{g?e}=\text{t}$ $\text{kimit?}=\text{e}$
 youth=ABS ANTIP=carry=3PL/AOR load=INS
 ‘(The) young men carried away a load.’

2. English (p.k.²)

- a. *John shot the lion.*
 b. *John shot at the lion.*

3.1. Is there a construction with a P argument demoted to an oblique in your language?

- a) yes.....
 b) no.....
 c)

3.1.1. Please provide a glossed, illustrative alternation with the P demoted to an oblique.

3.1.2. If P is demoted to an oblique, how it is flagged?

- a) by case marking.....
 b) by adposition.....
 c) by case marking and adposition...
 d)

² P.k. stands for personal knowledge.

3.1.3. If P is demoted to an oblique, is there any variation in the oblique flagging?

- a) yes.....
- b) no.....
- c)

3.1.4. Is the P demotion to an oblique triggered by a voice marker?

- a) yes.....
- b) no.....
- c)

3.1.5. Do all transitive verbs allow demoting P to an oblique?

- a) yes.....
- b) no.....
- c)

3.2. Oblique and affectedness

P demotion constructions with an oblique argument may correlate with a lower degree of affectedness of P. This leads to a partitive interpretation of the demoted P argument, as in (3), or imply that P is not necessarily or entirely affected by the action, as in (4) (but also 2 above). However, the correlation between a lower degree of affectedness and P oblique is not necessarily obligatory. In some languages, the verb does not imply that the oblique is partially affected or that the described activity did not succeed, as in (5) (but also 1 above).

3. Chamorro (Austronesian; Cooreman 1988: 576)

- a. *In-chule' i litratu.*
 ERG.1PL-take the picture
 'We took the picture.'
- b. *Man-mañule' ham gi litratu.*
 PL-ANTIP-take ABS.1PL LOC picture
 'We took some of the pictures.'

4. Chamorro (Austronesian, Malayo-Polynesian; Cooreman 1988: 548)

- a. *Un-patek i ga'lagu.*
 ERG.2SG-kick the dog
 'You kicked the dog.'
- b. *Mamatek hao gi ga'лаго.*
 ANTIP-kick ABS.2SG LOC dog
 'You kicked at the dog.'

5. West Greenlandic (Eskimo-Aleut; Sadock 1980: 306)

- a. *Angutip arnaq unatarpaa*
 man-REL woman(ABS) beat-IND-3SG.3SG
 'The man beat the woman.'

- b. *Angut arnamik unataavoq*
 man(ABS) woman-INS beat-ANTIP-IND-3SG
 ‘The man beat a woman.’

3.2.1. Does an oblique tend to correlate with a lower degree of affectedness in your language?

- a) yes.....
 b) no.....
 c)

3.2.2. If so, how is the oblique interpreted? (multiple answers are possible)

- a) partitive.....
 b) not entirely or fully affected.....
 c)

3.3. Oblique and referentiality

P demotion constructions with an oblique tend to reduce the degree of referentiality of P. Hence, a highly referential P argument becomes less identifiable (or ‘individuated’), receiving a nonreferential-indefinite reading, as in (6), or referential-indefinite interpretation, as in (7) (but also in 1, 5). However, the correlation between an oblique and reduced referentiality is not obligatory. In some languages, the oblique is still identified as a unique individual in the discourse, receiving a highly referential-definite interpretation, as in (8) (also in 2 and 4).

6. West Greenlandic (Eskimo-Aleut; Fortescue 1984: 86)

- a. *inuit tuqup-pai*
 people kill-3SG.3PL.IND
 ‘He killed the people.’
- b. *inun-nik tuqut-si-vuq*
 people-INS kill-ANTIP-3SG.IND
 ‘He killed people.’

7. Nez Percé (Sahaptian; Deal 2010: 85)

- a. *Cáan-nim páa-’ya’x-na ’inii-ne.*
 John-ERG 3/3-find-PFV house-OBJ
 ‘John found the house.’
- b. *Caan hi-’yáa’x-na ’iniit.*
 John 3SBJ-find-PFV house
 ‘John found a house.’

8. Warrungu (Pama-Nyungan; Tsunoda 1988: 599-600)

- a. *ngaya yina yangka-n*
 1SG.NOM 2SG.NOM search-PP
 ‘I looked/look for you.’
- b. *ngaya yinun-ku yangka-kali-n*
 1SG.NOM 2SG-DAT search-ANTIP-PP
 ‘I looked/look for you.’

3.3.1. Does an oblique correlate with a lower degree of referentiality in your language?

- a) yes.....
- b) no.....
- c)

3.3.2. If so, how is the oblique interpreted? (multiple answers are possible)

- a) as nonreferential-indefinite.....
- b) as nonreferential-generic.....
- c) as referential-indefinite.....

3.3.3. In case of the multiple answers in 3.3.2, could you please briefly explain what determines which interpretation is chosen/obligatory?

3.4. Oblique and animacy

The ability to demote the P argument to an oblique may depend on its animacy. In some languages, the P can be demoted to a peripheral oblique argument as long as it is low on the animacy scale, e.g. the P is inanimate, (9). In others, the P demotion to the peripheral argument is only possible when P is typically animate (human or non-human). Yet, in other languages, the mechanism of P demotion to an oblique is relatively indifferent to the animacy of P.

9. Bezhta (Nakh-Daghestanian; Comrie et al. 2021: 520)

- a. *öž-di* *xo* *y-üⁿq-čä*
 boy-OBL.ERG meat(IV) IV-eat-PRS
 ‘The boy eats the meat.’
- b. *öžö* *xo-lo-d* *Ø-ünq-dä-š*
 boy(I).ABS meat-OBL-INS I-eat-ANTIP-PRS
 ‘The boy is busy eating the meat.’

3.4.1. Does P demotion to an oblique depend to the P animacy in your language?

- a) yes.....
- b) no.....
- c)

3.4.2. If so, what is a predominate animacy pattern of the demoted P argument?

- a) oblique is predominantly inanimate
- b) oblique is predominantly animate (human or non-human)
- c)

4. P incorporation

Noun incorporation is a morphological operation that directly integrates a noun into the verb, resulting in a single complex predicate. A morphologically incorporated noun in the P function loses the properties of a full-fledged NP through the lack of compatibility with determiners. For instance, in (10b), the incorporated noun does not carry any more the accusative case. Noun juxtaposition (or ‘pseudo incorporation’) is also a form of noun incorporation (11). Even if it does not show any evidence of morphological compounding, the behavior of the noun is, to a large extent, comparable to a morphologically incorporated noun. Specifically, the juxtaposed noun is often incompatible with determiners and shows reduced mobility. For instance, in (11b), the juxtaposed noun ‘picture’ now follows immediately the verb and is not accompanied by ABS and PL adpositional markers as in the corresponding transitive construction (11a).

10. Kalamang (West Bomberai; Visser et al. 2019: 71)

- a. *ma muap-at paruo*
3SG food-ACC make
‘She is making (some) food.’
- b. *ma muap-paruo*
3SG food-make
‘She is cooking.’

11. Niuean (Austronesian; Seiter 1980: 70)

- a. *Kua tā he tama e tau fakatino.*
PERF draw ERG child ABS PL picture
‘The child has been drawing pictures.’
- b. *Kua tā fakatino e tama.*
PERF draw picture ABS child
‘The child has been drawing pictures/doing artwork.’

4.1. Is there a construction with a morphologically incorporated P in your language?

- a) yes.....
- b) no.....
- c)

4.1.1. If there is morphological P incorporation, is it triggered by a voice marker?

- a) yes.....
- b) no.....
- c)

4.1.2. If there is morphological P incorporation, do all transitive verbs participate in it?

- a) yes.....
- b) no.....
- c)

4.2. Is there a construction with pseudo-incorporation in your language?

- a) yes.....
- b) no.....
- c)

4.2.1. If there is pseudo-incorporation is it triggered by a voice marker?

- a) yes.....
- b) no.....
- c)

4.2.2. If there is pseudo-incorporation do all transitive verbs participate in it?

- a) yes.....
- b) no.....
- c)

4.3. Please provide a glossed, illustrative alternation with the P incorporation.

4.4. P incorporation and referentiality

Morphological and pseudo incorporation generally narrows the denotational sense of the verb, describing name-worthy, institutionalized, or unitary activities, as in (12-13). It typically answers the questions: “What are you occupied with? How do you spend your day?, where the focus is not on a specific P. This incorporation corresponds to Type I in Mithun (1984: 848). Hence, the referent of the P is nonspecific generic, as in (12b-13b). In the latter, the noun does not have a particular reference; instead, it qualifies the verb to which it is incorporated.

12. Ket (Yeniseian; Georg 2007: 235)

- a. *ād ítn dī⁸-b³-bed*
I yukola 1-3N-make
‘I make yukola.’
- b. *ād d[i]⁸-itn⁷-Ø³-i/bed*
I 1-yukola-3n-make
‘I yukola-make.’

13. Belhare (Sino-Thibetan; Bickel 2011: 2)

- a. *ina-ŋa wa khui[?]-t-u.*
DEM-ERG chicken[-NOM] [3SG.A-]steal-NPST-3SG.OBJ
‘That one steals / will steal the chicken.’

- b. *ina* *wa* *khuʔ-yu*.
 DEM[-NOM] chicken[-NOM] [3SG.S-]steal-NPST
 ‘That one steals chicken.’ (‘S/he is a chicken-stealer’)

Noun incorporation may play an active role in discourse (type III in Mithun 1984: 146). Hence the incorporated noun receives the referential interpretation. For instance, it can refer to definite nominal arguments with backgrounded old information as in (14). Specifically, in (14), noun incorporation backgrounds the established referent of the ‘ball’ in discourse. When mentioned for the first time, ‘ball’ is expressed as an independent NP only after it can be incorporated.

14. Mapudungun (Araucanian; Baker 2005: 146)

Kiñe *kelluwen* *rëtre-ke-Ø-y* *pali* *ñi* *tripalwe* *pële*
 one team push-HAB-3OBJ-IND.3SG.SBJ ball 3.POSS goal toward

kangelu *ingkawen* *katriitu-pali-ke-y*
 other side intercept-ball-HAB-3SG.SBJ

‘One team pushes the ball toward their foal, and the other side tries to intercept it.’

4.4.1. Does the incorporated P receive a nonreferential-generic reading in your language?

- a) yes.....
- b) no.....
- c)

4.4.2. Does the incorporated P argument receive a referential reading in your language?

- a) yes.....
- b) no.....
- c)

4.4.3. In case of the YES answer both in 4.4.1 and 4.4.2, could you please briefly explain what determines which interpretation is chosen/obligatory?

5. P suppression

The complete P demotion patterns may involve voice alternations in which the argument encoded like P in a transitive construction is syntactically suppressed (or ‘blocked’) by a voice marker. Even if the position occupied by this argument cannot be filled out by any argument expression, the patient role associated with this position is implied. Indeed, in (15b), when one skins, one must skin something.

15. Ainu (Isolate; Bugaeva and Kobayashi 2022: 529)

- a. *nea kamuy a-ri kor*
 that bear 4.A-skin when
 ‘When I skinned that bear . . .’
- b. *i-ri-an wa or-o wa sini-an na.*
ANTIP-skin-4.S and place-POSS and rest-4.S SPF
 ‘(Please stay!) I will skin (the catch, lit. ‘thing’) and then have a rest.’

5.1. Is there a construction with a syntactically suppressed P argument in your language?

- a) yes.....
- b) no.....
- c)

5.1.1. Do all transitive verbs allow for P suppression?

- a) yes.....
- b) no.....
- c)

5.1.2. Please provide a glossed, illustrative alternation with the syntactically suppressed P.

5.2. P suppression and referentiality

Constructions with a suppressed P argument often describe habitual or generalized activity, as in (16). They may also describe typical characteristics of the agent and/or its predisposition to perform specific actions. Consequently, they are limited to irrealis or generic sentences, where the suppressed P argument receives a nonreferential-generic interpretation, as in (16). Such P demotion constructions are known in the literature as “potential deobjective” (Haspelmath & Müller-Bardey 2004: 3; Holvoet & Daugavet 2020: 250). Constructions with a syntactically suppressed P argument can also describe a nonreferential-indefinite patient, often translated as ‘something’ (17), or represent a whole range of possible patients.

16. Masai (Nilotic; Payne D. 2021: 459)

M-ε-bárn-[†]i shó *ɔl=á-bárn-óní* *kewarié.*
 NEG-3-shave-ANTIP MSG=NMLZ-shave-NMLZ:AGENT night
 ‘A barber does not shave at night.’

17. Nivaçle (Mataguayan; Vidal & Payne D. 2021: 350)

- a. *xa-klôn* *ka* *nivakle*
 1-kill DET3 person
 ‘I killed a man.’
- b. *xa-vanka-klôn*
 1-ANTIP-kill
 ‘I kill/killed (someone).’

Less frequently, constructions with a suppressed P argument describe specific events that happen at the utterance time or have just happened and where the referent of the suppressed P argument is known to the speech act participants. The suppressed (or ‘blocked’) P argument receives a highly referential interpretation in such a context. For instance, in (18), the implicit patient of the verb *sx-ndza* ‘eat (someone)’ does not refer to ‘people’ in general but to the group of characters present at the moment of the action with the demoness. Consequently, the referent of the unexpressed P is referential and semantically recoverable from the context.

18. Japhug (Sino-Tibetan; Jacques 2021: 942)

tεe *ku-sx-ndza* *tu-oyuyu* *ri,*
 LNK SBJ:PCP-ANTIP-eat IPFV-prepare LNK
 ‘[The rākshasî demoness] (revealed her true nature) and was about to eat someone (one of them), but ...’

5.2.1. Does a suppressed P receive a nonreferential-generic reading in your language?

- a) yes.....
 b) no.....
 c)

5.2.2. Does a suppressed P receive a nonreferential-indefinite reading in your language?

- a) yes.....
 b) no.....
 c)

5.2.3. Does a suppressed P argument receive a referential reading in your language?

- a) yes.....
 b) no.....
 c)

5.2.4. In case of the YES answer in 5.2.1, 5.2.2, 5.2.3, could you please briefly explain what determines which interpretation is chosen/obligatory?

6. P omission

Verbs allowing for P omission have a flexible valency. In general, a flexivalent verb can be associated with two arguments or one. We are interested in these flexivalency alternations, in which A and S arguments remains agent,³ whereas the referent of the omitted P argument exists although it is not overtly expressed. For instance, in (19), when one slaughters one must slaughter something. Depending on the alignment pattern, the P omission may entail a change in the verbal morphology or not.⁴ For instance, in (19), S is encoded like A, and the two constructions show no other formal differences apart from the absence of the P argument. By contrast, in the P omission alternation in (20), the paradigm of A and P indexes in the inflection of the transitive verb is distinct from the paradigm of S indexes.

19. Moloko (Afro-Asiatic; Friesen et al. 2017: 288, 282)

- a. *Mana a-sl-ay* *awak*
 Mana 3SG+PFV-slay-CL goat
 ‘Mana slaughtered a goat.’
- b. *Mana a-sl-ay*
 Mana 3SG+PFV-slay-CL
 ‘Mana slaughtered [something].’

20. Abkhaz (Abkhaz-Adyge; O’Herin 2020: 481)

- a. *Ji-s-pa-wajt’*.
 3NH.SG.ABS-1SG.ERG-knit-PRS.IND.DYN
 ‘I am knitting it.’
- b. *S-pa-wajt’*
 1SG.ABS-knit-PRS.IND.DYN
 ‘I am (busy with) knitting.’

6.1. Is there a construction with an omitted P argument in your language?

- a) yes.....
- b) no.....
- c)

6.1.1. Do all transitive verbs allow for P omission?

- a) yes.....
- b) no.....
- c)

6.1.2. Please provide a glossed, illustrative alternation with the omitted P argument.

³ Consequently, the alternations exemplified by *I broke the vase* vs. *The vase broke* are excluded from our research.
⁴ Such alternations are discussed under different terms. For instance, Dixon (1994: 18) define alternations (19-20) as A-lability (Agent-preserving lability) or A-ambitransitivity (Agent-preserving ambitransitivity).

6.2. P omission and referentiality

P omission may lead to an unspecified or anaphoric reading,⁵ and only the former is relevant for P demotion patterns. We consider P omission with an unspecified reading as a particular kind of valency alternation, much like the expression of an unspecified A and an unspecified P that is a well-known function of passive and antipassive respectively (Creissels 2023: 518-519). The unspecified omitted P argument shows a reduced degree of referentiality to the extent that, in some contexts, it can receive a nonreferential-generic reading, as in (21) or nonreferential-indefinite interpretation, as in (22). Even if the referent of the omitted P argument potentially exists in (21-22), it cannot be semantically recovered from context.

21. English (p.k.)

- a. *He often reads books.*
- b. *He often reads.*

22. Japhug (Sino-Tibetan; Jacques 2021: 588)

- a. *nunu muntoɁ nu t^ha-taɁ tse,*
 DEM pattern DEM AOR:3→3'-weave LNK
 '[When] he wove this pattern, ...'
- b. *te^heme ci pu-taɁ nu-ŋu,*
 girl INDEF PST.IPFV-weave SENS-be
 'A girl was weaving (something).'

6.2.1. Does an omitted P argument receive a nonreferential-generic reading in your language?

- a) yes.....
- b) no.....
- c)

6.2.2. Does an omitted P argument receive a nonreferential-indefinite reading in your language?

- a) yes.....
- b) no.....
- c)

6.2.3. In case of the YES answer in 6.2.1 and 6.2.2 could you please briefly explain what determines which interpretation is chosen/obligatory?

⁵ We do not consider the omitted P with an anaphoric reading as an illustration of a P demotion pattern. This is because the anaphoric zero (or 'null') can be part of the pronominalization system, where the features necessary for the identification of the P referent are expressed by the index on the verb. The simplest case of zero anaphora is when the omitted P is obligatorily interpreted as definite whose referent can be deduced from the context.

References

- Baker, Mark C., Roberto Aranovich, and Lucía A. Golluscio. 2005. ‘Two Types of Syntactic Noun Incorporation: Noun Incorporation in Mapudungun and Its Typological Implications’. *Language* 81 (1): 138–76.
- Bickel, Balthasar. 2011. ‘Distributional Typology: Investigating the Theoretical and Methodological Foundations of a Probabilistic Approach to Linguistic Typology’.
- Bugaeva, Anna, and Miki Kobayashi. 2022. ‘Verbal Valency’. In *Handbook of the Ainu Language*, edited by Anna Bugaeva, 515–48. Boston: Mouton de Gruyter.
- Comrie, Bernard, Diana Forker, Zaira Khalilova, and Helma Van den Berg. 2021. ‘Antipassives in Nakh-Daghestanian Languages: Exploring the Margins of a Construction’. In *Antipassive: Typology, Diachrony, and Related Constructions*, edited by Katarzyna Janic and Alena Witzlack-Makarevich, 515–48. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Cooreman, Ann. 1988. ‘The Antipassive in Chamorro: Variations on the Theme of Transitivity’. In *Passive and Voice*, edited by Masayoshi Shibatani, 561–93. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Creissels, Denis. 2016. ‘Transitivity, Valency and Voice’. Porquerolles: European Summer School in Linguistic Typology.
- . 2023. *Transitivity, Valency, and Voice*. Oxford (UK): Oxford University Press.
- Deal, Amy R. 2010. ‘Ergative Case and the Transitive Subject: A View from Nez Perce’. *Natural Language and Linguistic Theory* 28 (1): 73–120.
- Dixon, R. M. W. 1994. *Ergativity*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Fortescue, Michael D. 1984. *West Greenlandic*. London: Croom Helm.
- Friesen, Dianne, Mana D. Isaac, Ali Gaston, and Mana Samuel. 2017. *A Grammar of Moloko*. Berlin: Language Science Press.
- Georg, Stefan. 2007. *A Descriptive Grammar of Ket (Yenisei-Ostyak): Part I: Introduction, Phonology and Morphology*. Global Oriental.
- Givón, Talmy. 2001. *Syntax: A Functional-Typological Introduction*. Vol. II. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Haspelmath, Martin. 2022. ‘Valency and Voice Constructions’.
- Haspelmath, Martin, and Thomas Müller-Bardey. 2004. ‘Valence Change’. In *Morphologie: Ein Internationales Handbuch Zur Flexion Und Wortbildung*, edited by G. E. Booij, Christian Lehmann, and Joachim Mugdan, 1130–45. Handbücher Zur Sprach- Und Kommunikationswissenschaft = Handbooks of Linguistics and Communication Science, 17.2. Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter.
- Holvoet, Axel, and Anna Daugavet. 2020. ‘Antipassive Reflexive Constructions in Latvian: A Corpus-Based Analysis’. *Baltic Linguistics* 11: 241–90.
- Jacques, Guillaume. 2021. *A Grammar of Japhug*. Berlin: Language Science Press.
- Kozinsky, Isaac, Vladimir P. Nadjalkov, and Maria S. Polinskaja. 1988. ‘Antipassive in Chukchee: Oblique Object, Object Incorporation, Zero Object’. In *Passive and Voice*, edited by Masayoshi Shibatani, 651–706. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Mithun, Marianne. 1984. ‘The Evolution of Noun Incorporation’. *Language* 60 (4): 847–94.

- O'Herin, Peter. 2020. 'Abaza and Abkhaz'. In *The Oxford Handbook of Languages of the Caucasus*, edited by Maria Polinsky, 447–48. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Payne, Doris L. 2021. 'The Profile and Development of the Maa (Eastern Nilotic) Antipassive'. In *Antipassive: Typology, Diachrony, and Related Constructions*, edited by Katarzyna Janic and Alena Witzlack-Makarevich. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Sadock, Jerrold. 1980. 'Noun Incorporation in Greenlandic: A Case of Syntactic Word Formation'. *Language* 56 (2): 300–319.
- Seiter, William J. 1980. 'Studies in Niuean Syntax'. Doctoral dissertation, University of California: San Diego.
- Tsunoda, Tasaku. 1988. 'Antipassive in Warrungu and Other Australian Languages'. In *Passive and Voice*, edited by Masayoshi Shibatani, 595–649. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Vidal, Alejandra, and Doris L. Payne. 2021. 'Polyfunctional Vanka- in Nivaçle and the Antipassive Category'. In *Antipassive: Typology, Diachrony, and Related Constructions*, edited by Katarzyna Janic and Alena Witzlack-Makarevich, 349–81. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Visser, Eline, Eva van Lier, and Marieke Olthof. 2019. 'The Semantics and Frequency of Incorporating Verbs in Kalamang'. Abstract.
- Zúñiga, Fernando, and Seppo Kittilä. 2019. *Grammatical Voice*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.